

The Digital Peripatetics Present

“Walk Like a *Lovaniensis*”

Profiling the Early Modern *Homo Academicus*
through the *Lovaniensia* Dataset

People of *Lovanium*

- ❖ Professors & students ♂
- ❖ Printers, artists, booksellers ♂((♀))
- ❖ Star-struck? Or data bias?
 - ❖ Erasmus (183 books) & Lipsius (124 books)
- ❖ P. A. Denique
 - ❖ A printer in the manuscript business?!

Lovanium or *Babel*?

- ❖ 10 languages
- ❖ *Lingua Latina dominatrix*
 - ❖ Alone (861) [not in graph]
 - ❖ In combination with Greek, French & Hebrew

Babel, is that you?

Talk of the town

- ❖ Religion and history rock
 - ❖ 1650-1700: Jansenists on the rise
 - ❖ 1750: Bye bye, Jansenists, bye bye
- ❖ Where are the sciences?
 - ❖ Medical revolution in 1700s? Or data bias?
- ❖ Late 1500s: “O Collegium Trilingue, where art thou?”

